

Social Effects Of Planned Re-Housing On Urban Poor; A Case Study Of Delhi

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Abstract

Urbanization is rapidly increasing across the globe, more so in the countries of third world. According to 2001 census of India, 285.35 million people lives in urban areas. It constitutes 27.8 percent of the total population of the India. In post -independence era while population of India has grown three times, the urban population has grown five times. The rising urban population has also given rise to increase in the number of urban poor. As per 2001 estimates, the slum population is estimated to be 61.8 million. And it is expected to grow phenomenally. And so will pose a problem that will have its bearing on social institution and of course put a pressure on the existing infrastructure of the cities and towns. Traditional methods and mechanisms of urban planning are becoming outmoded in meeting the challenges of urbanization; the economic liberalization in India further fueled the growth of Indian cities, which are becoming growth engines of the country's economy. Yet many cities are not in a position to cope with economic development pressure in a sustainable manner due to the lack of processes, mechanisms and forward planning.

Keywords

Slum, Planning Settlement, Urban Housing, Development Deterioration.

Introduction

The hard core reality of urban poverty can be characterized by high population density at urban slums lack of adequate housing and services associated with provision of water, sanitation and drainage. Re-housing slum dwellers in 'normal' accommodation is a basic ingredient of the social reintegration process, because of the power of 'normality' and the values that have historically been constructed around living at/having a 'home' - freedom, security, privacy, comfort. The persistence of the fragile situations set the limits of reintegration. Keeping in view all these, it has become imperative to draw up a coherent urbanization policy/strategy to implement projects in cities and towns.

Historically, re-housing efforts were directed to the clearance of 'unfit' dwellings and the provision of better ones, invariably with public health as the major incentive to action. Physical factors are also more obvious to those taking policy decisions about housing. Physical criteria of housing standards are easier to establish. Housing is regarded as social services. This in some sense, basic to the whole idea of the welfare state, particularly in its local government context.

Government of India in December 2005 had started 'Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission' (JnNURM) this has two components: a- 'Basic Services to Urban Poor' (BSUP) in 63 chosen cities, Delhi is among one of them, b- 'Integrated Housing & Slum Development Programme' (IHSDP) one of the major aim of these (BSUP & IHSDP) is an integrated approach in ameliorating the conditions of the urban slum dwellers who do not possess adequate shelter and reside in dilapidated conditions.

Objective of study

1. To analyze the dynamics of locality: Whether people belong to land or land belongs to people.
2. Whether urban renewal programmer had achieved one of its major purposes, by helping those who lived in slums.
3. To find out the structural and institutional obstacles these people (homeless/slum dwellers) encounter with access to housing & work.

Review of Literature

As cities age, they usually begin to deteriorate physically. Though difficult to measure precisely, serious physical deterioration is commonly referred to as blight. A blighted area is one that has lost its attractiveness for all its former uses; consequently, its buildings and installations have been allowed to fall into deterioration.

The older central cities are most likely to contain deteriorated structures. A common practice is for owners to convert obsolete buildings into housing units while waiting for some commercial enterprise to bid for the land, thus generating slums. A slum may be defined by physical as well as social characteristics, including structural decay, lack of plumbing, and a high ratio of occupants to rooms. In addition to inadequate housing, slums are also characterized by congestion, lack of recreational space and neglect to neighborhood facilities. The considerable amount of attention social scientists and policymakers have given to blighted areas of inner cities can be misleading.

Methodology

Research design will be descriptive; as the purpose of the research is to describe about the re-housed. Schedule method, will be employed for data collection; for the fact that

researcher has a perceived notion that considerable number of person in the re-housed locality will be illiterate. Question will be of simple; yes/no or multiple choice. And there will be no scope for opinions and narratives; that might be deconstructed in many different ways, which might lead to discrepancies in result. In methodological parlance I will be using 'Triangulation method' which can be defined as the sequential execution of two or more primary studies of the same phenomenon using different methods. It is based on the logic where the respective strong aspects of the one method supposedly joined forces and supposedly cancelling out their respective weak aspects.

In order to substantiate the findings, researcher will also be using interview method and focus group discussion. Although researcher has plan for a well structured methodology, he has a very strong positive notion about the 'Process Research'

Analysis

The urban renewal projects were intended to raze slum areas and construct high rise apartments for the poor. Although urban renewal programmes have had some positive impact on central city areas, they have received a disproportionate amount of criticism. A basic deficiency is that while substandard housing was destroyed, it was frequently replaced upper middle class residence or commercial buildings. In many cases the improved housing either never occurred or greatly inconvenienced them by moving them far from their original neighborhood.

The national housing policy in 1988 recognized that the role of government should be an initiator rather than home builder. The government should facilitate access to land, material, technology and finance. Delhi today is emerging as one of the largest cities in the world. From a settlement of 23 lakh in 1961, its population increased to 138 lakh in 2001, at a growth rate of around 4.6 % (1991- 2001) as a result there is phenomenal pressure on land, housing, transportation network and services. Out of a total area nearly 50 % has already been urbanized and the rest is under heavy pressure of urbanization. In spite of the plans for decentralization and to restrict the growth of the city by development of the National capital Region (NCR), the runaway growth of Delhi continues. It is projected that Delhi in the year 2021 will have a population of about 230 lakh, putting severe strain and demand on land , physical infrastructure, transport, ecology and environment, housing and resources.

City planners are caught in dilemma. They want to purge the city of the most deteriorated buildings, which are unsightly and sometimes dangerous. They want to reduce crowding, improve the physical environment, admit light and air, and bring trees and grass to the heart of the city. But their aspirations are more frequent than not frustrated by the scarcity and the high values of land that dictate intensive use and dense occupancy. Housing projects, therefore, tend to increase the number of person per acre even though the amount of space between buildings is greater than before the slums were cleared. Second only to density dilemma is the diversity dilemma. Many city designers try to develop areas as large and homogeneous units. They plan in "super blocks" in order to gain open space. Recently, however, city planners have become sensitive to the consequences of earlier policies that began urban renewal by knocking down everything in the neighborhoods. Slum clearance without reference to prior land use destroys neighborhoods and substitutes environments without past and personality.

A recent position takes as its objectives not the construction of garden cities but the rehabilitation of established neighborhoods and the preservation of original buildings, whenever possible without displacing its residents. This viewpoint pleads for neighborhood diversity through these means: (1) a "close -grained mix" of ground -floor stores and residences, (2) the preservation of short blocks, which tend to increase the possibility of neighboring, (3) the preservation of old buildings to give a sense of continuity and architectural variety, and (4) high density with much of the land covered by buildings.

In her argument for a "close-grained mix" Jacobs shows that sidewalks for example, perform social functions beyond their manifest use: (1) the busy foot traffic of a well used city street makes the street safe for women and children because the street is constantly under surveillance from its windows, stoops, and shops. (2) The street is a location for unorganized play and for socialization of children by neighbors as well as peers. (3) The sidewalk and its shops are a communication network and a place where privacy is balanced against varying kinds of contact, but the emphasis on association at arm's length is an urban value.

The great uniform areas of office buildings stand in stark contrast to the round- the-clock activity of heterogeneous used blocks. In Washington, D.C for example, massive and homogenous offices covers acre after acre. Some of the buildings are admirable - if it is assumed that every building ought to be a monument- and the lawns lend a park- like quality to the city. But the center of a national bureaucracy, vigorously active during the working day, becomes at night a desert populated by a few janitors and police. Belatedly there has been a shift in the thinking of Washington planners. It is expected that new office needs will be met by smaller buildings located in the midst of residential areas in which at least some of the workers might live. The official buildings and their grounds would add variety to neighborhoods without overwhelming them. Washington then might become something less of a park to be looked at by tourists but something more of a city in which the nation's business is conducted and in which people live.

Utility

Government of India had started a 'Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban renewal mission' (JNNURM) in December 2005. This mission has to cover most of the Indian cities through its sub programmes, namely 'Basic services to Urban poor' (BSUP) & 'Integrated Housing and Slum development Programme' (IHSDP). Major component of these two sub programmes is housing for the poor. Present study will try to critically evaluate the outcome of the (JNNURM). Further this study hope to provide impetus to urban sociology in India; which in recent time not getting the deserved attention from the sociologists. As it will allow concepts to emerge from the data, and allow researcher to develop a dialogue between his discipline (sociology) and his field of study. Moreover, it would be a handbook for policy markers, town planners and implementers of the urban renewal programme.

Findings

After conducting this study researcher found out that the migrants as well as the urban people rehoused faced several problems like sanitation slum like situation and mental hygiene. The urban rehoused inhabitants in Delhi could not get proper drainage water supply and open space for children.

Conclusion

Taking clue from previous researches, and from the available literature on the subject. I can say that re-housing weaken the caste, regional, lingual, religious and cultural considerations. And facilitates the formation of area sabhas as the residents are now more into community participation. There might be an initial problem of adjustment in these new settlements because human beings are tend to behave in a habitual way; and they belongs to locality rather than locality belong to human beings. Although children feel safe while playing in these organized locality as there is a marked area for every human activity; women in particular younger lot do not feel safe and secure in these isolated clusters.

Urban renewal programme such as JNNURM, has to go a long way to completely do away with slum in cities like Delhi. As there seems to be many structural as well as institutional obstacles before slum dwellers.

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